

ISic4374

Fragmentary Latin inscription

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found during rescue excavations in 2015, in the area immediately to the north of the Cimitero Comunale, in surface layers above Roman period tombs within a late-antique basilica

Coordinates

37.990150, 13.689428

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese

Physical Description

Block of stone broken on all sides

Dimensions

Height 40 cm

Width 30 cm

Depth 25 cm

Layout

Remains of two lines of Latin letters, vacat above, beginning and end of lines are lost

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregular letters, fairly broad and well spaced. P and R are closed, C is more than a semi-circle

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. [---](vac.undefined)Caprili!!--]

2. [---]proc[---]

Apparatus**Translation****Commentary**

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Chiovaro, Monica, Rondinella, Maria Teresa 2017. Nuove scoperte nelle necropoli di Termini Imerese. *Notiziario Archeologico della Soprintendenza di Palermo*. 22: 1-31. At 27 fig.75

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